

Identification and Authentication of Copper Canisters for Spent Nuclear Fuel by a Portable Ultrasonic System

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Abstract—The long-term storage of nuclear-spent fuel in geological repositories has introduced the need to develop new technologies for safeguarding the fuel. Continuity of knowledge about the fuel’s location must be maintained during transport of the copper canisters that contain the fuel from the encapsulation plant to the final repository. Among the possible different containment and surveillance measures are the identification and authentication of each canister. The authors propose an innovative solution for this purpose, which is based on the ultrasonic acquisition of two fingerprints: an artificial code realized by chamfers machined in the inner surface of the copper lid (identification) and a natural signature due to the weld between the lid and the tube (authentication). Several prototypes of ultrasonic acquisition devices have been developed and tested on real copper samples to validate the identification and authentication concepts. This article describes the design of a new, optimized version of the ultrasonic acquisition device. The aim of this new design is to provide a solution for the identification and authentication of copper canisters using a portable device that is cost-effective and easy to use, which does not require the presence of an inspector in the field. The mechanical design of the reader has been upgraded with the introduction of a stepper motor and a new probe holder that includes a beam splitter to acquire two fingerprints simultaneously. The new device has been tested on copper samples, both with and without chamfers, and the results are reported in this article. The implementation of the seal fingerprint acquisition device (SFAD) within the new portable acquisition system is discussed at the end of this article with the goal of improving the electronic performance of the acquisition device in the field.

Index Terms—Authentication, copper canisters, electronic system, identification, nuclear-spent fuel, ultrasonic techniques.

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I. INTRODUCTION

THE concept of long-term storage of spent nuclear fuel in deep geological repositories has become established as a means to keep long-lived radioactive wastes contained and isolated from humans and from the environment for thousands of years. In Sweden, the Swedish Nuclear Fuel and Waste Management Company (SKB), Solna, Sweden, developed a method for the safe disposal of spent nuclear fuel [1]. This “multibarrier” concept would provide isolation by a combination of engineered and natural barriers (rock, salt, and clay) without any obligation for future generations to actively maintain the facility. Copper canisters with iron inserts will be used as the first shield for fuel assemblies (see Fig. 1). The encapsulation of the fuel will take place at the encapsulation plant facility that will be built in Oskarshamn, Sweden. At this stage, copper canisters will also be sealed with copper lids by a friction stir welding (FSW) process. Afterward, canisters will be transported to the final repository in Forsmark (Sweden) for the deposition in tunnels and later will be covered by the bentonite clay. According to the Swedish project, this geological repository will include about 66 km of tunnels excavated 500-m underground in the bedrock, and around 6000 canisters will be stored in the facility with an average deposition of one canister per day [2].

Throughout handling, transport, and deposition of the canisters, from the encapsulation plant to the final repository, containment and surveillance measures have to be used to maintain the continuity of knowledge of the spent nuclear fuel. A possible option is to create a single fingerprint for each copper container in order to discriminate between containers (identification) and to provide evidence of falsification attempts (authentication). External engraving on the surface of canisters should be avoided since it could damage the canister’s integrity, triggering a corrosion process. Therefore, alternative tagging solutions have to be developed to uniquely identify each canister (identification fingerprint) and check if the lid has been opened and closed again with a new weld (authentication fingerprint). A comparison between potential tagging technologies already used in the nuclear field can be found in [3]. Among the different solutions, ultrasonic techniques stand out for their capacity to penetrate materials

Fig. 1. Partial section of a copper canister with iron insert hosting a spent fuel assembly.

to record intrinsic features without external engraving. As a consequence, the Seals and Identification Laboratory (SILab), Joint Research Centre of the European Commission, Ispra, Italy, in collaboration with the Ultrasonic and NDT Laboratory, University of Florence, Florence, Italy, developed an innovative method based on ultrasound for the identification and authentication of copper canisters [4], [5]. This new approach is based on the acquisition of two ultrasonic fingerprints: an “artificial” and “natural” one. The first is the amplitude response of a unique configuration of chamfers, symmetrical sloping surfaces at the edge of the inner surface of the copper lid (identification fingerprints). The second is the amplitude response of the internal gap between the lid and canister after FSW (authentication fingerprints). Several tests have been performed by previous authors to validate both concepts in the laboratory, and different acquisition prototypes have been developed and tested. The statistical verification of the identification and authentication concepts has not yet been accomplished since the number of samples available for tests was not sufficient to implement statistical analysis. This article presents the description of a new ultrasonic device, optimized for reducing the acquisition time of the collection of both fingerprints by using only one ultrasonic probe and a beam splitter. Following a brief introduction of the main aspects of the ultrasonic method, we describe the mechanical and electronic design of the new acquisition device. The experimental test of the new system was carried out on slices of a welded copper lid fabricated using standard procedures [6], where a series of chamfers with different geometries are machined. The results of the inspection are analyzed and compared with signals acquired before the manufacturing of the chamfers. After a discussion of the results, in Section IV, we propose an improvement in the hardware and software performance of the acquisition system. This improvement comes from the introduction of the seal fingerprint acquisition device (SFAD) for the transmission/reception of signals to/from the probe via an SPI bus, the control of the motor, and the wireless transmission of data to a remote unit.

II. ULTRASONIC METHOD

The study of copper canisters’ geometry and acoustic properties is an extremely important preliminary step in the development of an identification and authentication method for canisters based on ultrasound. This paragraph describes

Fig. 2. Geometry of the top lid of the copper canister and nondestructive testing of the FSW from the top of the lid using a phase array probe. Source: SKB.

the approach proposed by the authors for the collection of fingerprints contained within each canister, which is detectable from the outside by an ultrasonic immersion transducer.

A. Mechanical Design and Acoustic Properties of Copper Canisters

Canisters are big cylinders (4835-mm high and 1050-mm diameter) consisting of a copper shell and a nodular cast iron insert with steel channel tubes; the fuel assemblies are placed into such tubes. The total weight of a copper canister with the fuel inside is about 24 600 kg [7]. The outer shell is composed of a bottom plate, a tube, and a lid made entirely made of copper. Copper is selected for a combination of factors, including heat transfer and stress handling properties, chemical and corrosion resistance, and stability in pure water. Since canisters are designed to provide a sufficient containment of the fuel over a long period of time, the minimal copper thickness of the shell should be 50 mm (considering also the welds). In particular, the design tolerances imposed are 49 ± 0.3 mm for the tube, 50 ± 0.6 mm for the lid, and 48.5 ± 0.7 mm for the welds. The copper tube is manufactured from extrusion by means of semicontinuous casting, whereas the lid/base is manufactured by continuous casting: a solid ingot is heated up, forged in several different steps by a press, and finally machined. As a result, the average copper grain size is lower than $350 \mu\text{m}$ [8]. However, the grain size can vary in the weld zone between the copper lid and the tube. In fact, during the FSW process, a rotating tool penetrates the interface between lid and tube, heats up the material, and creates a weld joint, rotating 360° all around the circumference of the lid. After the welding process, several tests, including the nondestructive testing by ultrasound, are performed to verify the quality of the weld (see Fig. 2).

The velocity of sound in copper canisters is approximately 4660 m/s for longitudinal waves and 2260 m/s for shear waves. The attenuation of sound can vary depending on the inspection frequency and the copper inner structure; according to [9], the attenuation in copper can vary from 50 to 200 dB/m at 5 MHz, depending on the grain size. Concerning the identification and authentication of canisters, preliminary ultrasonic tests have been carried out by the authors on copper flanges

(or rather slices, 22° and 50° extended, of entire copper lids already welded onto tubes) that were provided by SKB to the SILab with the aim of selecting the best ultrasonic probe for the acquisition of echoes from copper canisters. The transducer selection is strictly related to the type of discontinuity to be detected; in terms of inspection frequency, the definition of the discontinuity's geometry, and distance from the probe is important elements to reach a compromise between resolution and attenuation. The use of a phased array probe was discarded, and instead, a single transducer was used since it was an easy solution that was effective and cost-efficient.

Before focusing on the design of the ultrasonic acquisition tool, it is worth summarizing the most important requirements of the ultrasonic method.

B. Identification Fingerprint by a Unique Code of Chamfers

According to the Nuclear Safeguards requirements, a tagging system must provide a unique identity to each canister and provide evidence of counterfeiting or duplication attempts. For this purpose, the proposed ultrasonic method is based on the combination of two fingerprints that angularly match together, producing a third unique fingerprint. The current identification concept proposed by the authors is the result of numerous analyses carried out in a preliminary phase of the research. Originally, unique configurations of flat bottom holes (FBHs) were supposed to be drilled on the inner surface of the copper lid to create a code that is readable from the top of the lid by an ultrasonic transducer [10]. This solution respected the minimum limit of 50 mm for the copper thickness but suffered from high attenuation of the signal. Therefore, in order to implement an automated scanning procedure, the position of the probe has been relocated, and FBHs have been replaced with chamfers. A chamfer is a transitional edge between the two surfaces of the copper lid. To date, the identification fingerprint is represented by the ultrasonic amplitude response of unique configurations of chamfers machined around the inner surface of the copper lid before welding. Chamfers must be located where the copper thickness is more than 50 mm. From the outside, an ultrasonic probe, kept inclined at fixed height “*h*,” can receive the ultrasonic echo reflected by chamfers according to Snell's law (see Fig. 3).

The ultrasonic test is performed using a pulse-echo excitation of the probe, and water is employed as a coupling medium. The ultrasonic amplitude response is collected considering the maximum amplitude within a certain time window (programmable gate). Whenever a chamfer is encountered, the amplitude of the echo increases; conversely, when the chamfer is not present, the amplitude of the echo decreases. For the definition of the time gate, it is important to calculate the expected time of flight (TOF) of the chamfers' echoes in the following equation. In particular, V_W and V_C are the speed of sound in water (about 1481 m/s at 20 °C) and in copper (4660 m/s), respectively, whereas D_1 and D_2 represent the water path and the geometrical distance between the center of a chamfer and the impact point of the ultrasonic beam at the

Fig. 3. Ultrasonic immersion testing of chamfers, machined in an area where the copper thickness is higher than the minimum “ T_{min} ” of 50 mm. The inclination α_1° of the transducer is chosen in accordance with the slope α_2° of the chamfers according to Snell's law where V_w is the velocity of sound in water (about 1481 m/s at 20 °C) and V_c is the velocity of sound in copper (4660 m/s).

boundary between water and copper

$$\text{TOF} = \left[\frac{2 \cdot D_1}{V_w} \right] + \left[\frac{2 \cdot D_2}{V_c} \right]. \quad (1)$$

By a complete rotation (360°) of the transducer around the copper lid circumference, the acquired amplitude response will present peaks and valleys depending on the presence of a chamfer or not. Therefore, the machining of unique configurations of chamfers can produce an identification signature detectable by ultrasound [11]. The definition of the chamfers' width, slope, and angular extension is important to realize a unique pattern of chamfers for each canister. Simulations with CIVA software [12] revealed that a good compromise between not affecting the geometry of the canister too much and having a good signal-to-noise ratio in the ultrasonic inspection (20 dB at least) is to use a 10-mm chamfer that is 55° inclined and 3° wide. Concerning the arrangements of chamfers around the lid circumference, the original idea of using a binary code has been replaced with the codification illustrated in Fig. 4. The circumference is divided into four sections corresponding to units, tens, hundreds, and thousands of digits, starting from a reference chamfer which is 6° wide. Each section is divided into nine slots of 3°, and depending on which slot is occupied or not by a chamfer, a unique ID number is created for each container. Hence, with this solution, it could be possible to uniquely identify more than 6000 canisters using only four chamfers plus a reference. Moreover, only 26 g of copper would be removed from the 708 kg of a copper lid. Chamfers are arranged all around the circumference because the identification code must be angularly matched with the authentication fingerprint, as illustrated in the following.

The identification concept is necessary for the discrimination of copper canisters but is not sufficient to prevent falsification attempts. For this purpose, the combination with the authentication fingerprint has been suggested by the authors.

C. Authentication Fingerprint From the Inspection of the Welding Area

The ultrasonic beam can penetrate into the material and is reflected whenever it encounters discontinuity. The FSW

Fig. 4. Example of chamfers code around the copper lid circumference for the unique identification of a canister with the ID number 4623.

Fig. 5. Ultrasonic immersion testing for the investigation of the welding area between copper lid and tube. The probe is kept at a fixed height perpendicular to the welding line in order to receive echoes from the internal gap and the external wall.

process between the copper lid and tube includes the presence of an air gap beneath the weld joint line at the end of the welding process. This gap represents a discontinuity in the material, detectable by an ultrasonic probe kept at a fixed height “ h ,” perpendicular to the welding line, as shown in Fig. 5. By rotating the probe around the whole lid circumference, the amplitude response of the internal gap can be acquired. Depending on the welding process, the height of the gap can vary around the circumference, and it is then possible that the ultrasonic beam also penetrates up to the external wall. In this case, it means that in that area, the lid and tube are completely welded because the gap is not detectable.

Since the amplitude of the internal gap echo changes depending on the welding process and the inner structure of the material in the surroundings of the joint line, this signal could be used as an authentication fingerprint for copper canisters. The variation of the signal is strictly related to material properties, such as the copper grain size after the FSW process, which could be unique for each canister. However, the uniqueness of such a fingerprint has not yet been demonstrated because

Fig. 6. Ultrasonic amplitude response of the internal gap (in blue) and the external wall (in red) on varying on the angular position of the probe kept at height “ h ” of 28 mm. Between 177° and 206° , the inflection of both curves represents the area where the tool crossing twice during the welding process.

of the cost difficulties in the procurement of real copper canister samples for statistical analysis. However, the first experimental tests carried out on three real samples of copper lids that were already welded have revealed the presence of several peculiarities in acquired echoes. An example, shown in Fig. 6, is the point where the tool crosses twice during the FSW process that is clearly detectable in each investigated sample; the crossing point is revealed as a peak/valley in the amplitude ultrasonic response of the internal gap/external wall. The amplitude of the echoes reported in the chart is relative to the reference voltage of 5 V of the A/D converter; acquired data are digitized on 255 levels (8-bit resolution). The view gram is plotted with a full-scale value adjusted to highlight the dynamics of the signals. A more detailed description of the acquisition board is reported in Section III-A.

The angular matching between the amplitude response of chamfers (identification fingerprint) and the amplitude response of the internal gap (authentication fingerprint) can create a third unique fingerprint, even more robust against falsification attempts.

D. Integration Between the Fingerprints by a Single Probe and a Beam Splitter

The acquisition of the identification and authentication fingerprints can be implemented using two probes or a single probe with an adjustable inclination to carry out a double inspection. In both cases, the electronics requires a complex structure, and the time for acquisition and processing of data can be long. For this purpose, another measurement setup consisting of a single probe and a beam splitter has been proposed by the authors. According to this configuration, the ultrasonic beam can be split into two directions for the inspection of both the chamfers and the internal gap. As shown in Fig. 7, the ultrasonic probe is kept at a fixed inclination due to a stainless steel holder having a sloped surface that acts as a mirror for ultrasound. In this way, the split ultrasonic beam can be directed both to the chamfers and to the internal gap.

This new solution offers simple control electronics for the transmission and reception of data to and from a single ultrasonic transducer and an excellent temporal and spatial correlation between these two reflection signals. In this case, the selection of the most suitable probe and the choice of its position, in terms of height, become crucial for the success of the ultrasonic investigation.

Fig. 7. Ultrasonic acquisition of the identification and authentication fingerprints by a single probe and a beam splitter. The echoes from chamfers (point 1), interface water/copper (point 2), and internal gap (point 3) can be acquired by the transducer in immersion testing.

In fact, the lateral and axial resolutions of the probe should not only be sufficient to detect the presence of a chamfer but also to reveal changes in the internal gap. In order to identify the best solution, the new setup of measurements has been simulated with CIVA software, and the results have been analyzed [13]. Simulations pointed to the possibility of realizing an ultrasonic inspection of chamfers and the internal gap simultaneously using a water path of 20 mm and a probe height of 24 mm. The speed of sound considered for simulations was 1481 m/s in water and 4651 m/s in copper; in this first analysis, the attenuation of ultrasound has been neglected to study only the propagation direction of the ultrasonic beam with the beam splitter. The probe used in the simulation was a 10-MHz immersion transducer with a 0.5-in element diameter and an 8.4-in spherical focused distance. As shown in Fig. 8, the A-scan view of simulated echoes shows three main peaks at different TOFs corresponding to the echo of the chamfer (TOF_1), the echo of the interface between water/copper (TOF_2), and the echo of the internal gap (TOF_3).

Therefore, by rotating the ultrasonic probe with the beam splitter around the canister's circumference, it should be possible to collect the identification and authentication fingerprints in only one round, preserving the spatial and temporal coherence of data. Afterward, the two fingerprints can be angularly overlapped, and a third unique fingerprint can be realized. This new signature can be recorded in addition to the other two in order to increase the robustness of the method and prevent falsification attempts. Even in the ideal case of a perfect duplication of the identification code of chamfers, if the angular matching between them is not the same, the correlation between the reference and the new third fingerprint will be low.

III. ULTRASONIC ACQUISITION DEVICE: DESIGN, DEVELOPMENT, AND TESTING

Originally, the ultrasonic acquisition system was conceived by the authors as a big cylinder including a water tank for immersion testing, the control electronics, and two probes:

Fig. 8. A-scan view of the inspection simulation carried on a copper flange with a probe and the beam splitter on a time window of 135 μs . Three peaks are clearly detectable at the TOF of 64.3, 88.16, and 110.7 μs correspondent, respectively, to chamfers, interface water/copper, and internal gap. The smallest echoes at about (A) 29 and (B) 58 μs are the reflections on the first interface water copper and the interface water/mirror.

the first for the detection of chamfers' code (identification fingerprint) and the second for the acquisition of the amplitude responses of the welding area (authentication fingerprint). By a 360° rotation of the whole structure, the two signatures would be recorded and saved for the postprocessing and the angular matching [14]. Subsequently, the design of the acquisition device has been modified and adapted for the inspection of copper canisters by a single probe and a beam splitter. This section describes the design and realization of the new system prototype and its testing on a copper flange with chamfers. The aim of this study is to evaluate the performance of the device on varying chamfer geometry and position.

A. Mechanical and Electronic Design of the Ultrasonic Acquisition Device

The mechanical structure of the ultrasonic device for the simultaneous collection of the identification and authentication fingerprints can be seen as an optimization of a previous version. The latter has been developed for the investigation of the welding area of copper canisters during a measurement session at the SKB's Canister Laboratory, Oskarshamn. As described in [15], the system was composed of a reader, an electronics box, and a computer to process and display received data. The reader was made of three supporting arms to center the system above the lid and a rotating bar to support the transducer perpendicular to the welding area. The rotation of the probe was ensured by a synchronous motor, which allowed a complete rotation of the transducer in about 4 min. The control box included a 220–24-V ac inverter to power the motor and the US-KEY module (Lecoeur Electronique) dedicated to the transmission/reception of signals to/from the probe via a USB connection. In order to speed up the acquisition of ultrasonic responses and implement a double inspection of copper canisters using a single probe and a beam splitter, a new version of the ultrasonic acquisition device has been designed. The new rotating reader includes three angular arms spaced at 120° to center the system above the lid, and a rotating bar holds the ultrasonic transducer (see Fig. 9). In this

Fig. 13. Results of the inspection simulation of the copper flange with seven chamfers. The B-scan view and the amplitude response on varying of the probe displacement is shown (left, top to bottom). The A-scan view and the 3-D drawing of the simulated setup are reported (right). A is the peak’s amplitude of each chamfer, whereas E is the angular extension.

drawing of chamfers has been realized with SolidWorks, and a configuration is reported in Fig. 12. Chamfers are arranged in the inner surface of the copper lid and present the same slope but with different widths and angular extensions. The different chamfers’ geometry has been done on purpose to verify which is the most suitable for a good identification code. All chamfers are inclined at 55° and have a width of 10 mm, except for chamfers C3 and C4 that have a width of 6 and 8 mm, respectively. Indeed, chamfers C1, C2, and C7 are extended 1°, 2°, and 6°, respectively, whereas all the others are 3°.

According to the coding proposed by authors for the identification of canisters (see Fig. 4), the minimal distance between two adjacent chamfers is 3°. Before machining the pattern of chamfers on the copper flange, CIVA software simulations are performed to verify that such configuration of chamfers is clearly detectable by an ultrasonic probe at a 15° inclination according to Snell’s Law. A scanning angle of 50° is imposed on the probe, and the ultrasonic echoes are examined on variations of the displacement. According to the probe direction, C1 is the first chamfer encountered. The outcome of the inspection simulation is illustrated in Fig. 13.

As illustrated in Fig. 13, the chart of the amplitude response of chamfers presents seven peaks corresponding to the seven chamfers; all chamfers can be clearly detected by the ultrasonic probe, and the peaks’ amplitude is correlated with the corresponding width and angular extension. As shown in Table I, for the same width, the amplitude of the relative peak is proportional to the angular extension of the chamfer. The amplitude values reported in Table I are negative since in CIVA, the strongest echo resulted from a simulation set to 0 dB, and then, the amplitude of all the other echoes is relative to this reference.

Following the simulations, the manufacturing of chamfers was done with a computer numerical control (CNC) milling machine (model C.B.Ferrari B13). Since the lid was already welded onto the tube in the flange, the manufacturing process involves the removal of a part of the tube for the successful realization of chamfers (see Fig. 14).

TABLE I
SIMULATED VALUES OF THE PEAK’S AMPLITUDE “A” AND ANGULAR EXTENSION “E” OF THE ULTRASONIC ECHO OF CHAMFERS

Chamfers	A [dB]	E [°]	Width [mm]
C1	-7.9	0.8	10
C2	-0.6	2.2	10
C3	-7.9	2.8	6
C4	-4.6	3	8
C5	-0.6	3	10
C6	-0.3	3.2	10
C7	-0.6	6.4	10

In reality, the chamfers should be machined on the inner surface of the copper lid before the FSW process. However, because of the high cost of the welding process, the heavy-weight of an entire copper lid, and the limited availability of welded samples, the test of the new ultrasonic acquisition device has been implemented in laboratory on a copper flange where chamfers have been machined afterward.

C. Experimental Tests on the Copper Flange With Chamfers

The ultrasonic test of the ultrasonic device on the copper flange with chamfers was carried out using the V311 immersion transducer (10 MHz of central frequency, 0.5-in element diameter, 8.4-in spherical focused, and 73.36% of -6-dB bandwidth), inclined with $\alpha_1^\circ = 15^\circ$ and fixed at height $h = 24$ mm. As shown in Fig. 15, the flange with chamfers has been positioned at 120° from the other two flanges in order to replicate an entire lid. The investigation of the copper flange is performed by immersion testing considering a water path of about 21 mm.

According to simulations shown in Fig. 8, the collection of the identification and authentication fingerprints is implemented establishing three different time windows (gates) for the acquisition of the chamfers echo, the interface water-copper echo, and the internal gap echo. The temperature of the water during the test was 23 °C. The setting of the US-KEY was an amplifier gain of 45 dB, an impulse of 200-V peak, duration of 80 ns, and a P.R.F. = 1 kHz. The maximum amplitude echoes acquired within gates 1 and 3 on variations of the probe displacement are shown in Fig. 16. The value of amplitude is relative to the maximum amplitude received within all gates.

The seven chamfers are clearly detectable; the amplitude response of chamfers presents seven peaks whose amplitude and angular extensions are in accordance with the geometry of each chamfer. In particular, the measured peak’s amplitude values and the angular extensions are reported in Table II. In agreement with simulations where the width is equal, the higher the angular extension of the chamfer, the higher the peak of amplitude.

Concerning the internal gap echo, the acquired amplitude response should be compared with the amplitude response

Fig. 14. Manufacturing of chamfers on a copper flange by a CNC machine.

TABLE II

MEASURED VALUES OF THE PEAK'S AMPLITUDE "A" AND ANGULAR EXTENSION "E" OF THE ULTRASONIC ECHO OF CHAMFERS

Chamfers	A [a.u.]	E [°]	Width [mm]
C1	127	1.2	10
C2	213	2.1	10
C3	145	3	6
C4	178	2.9	8
C5	208	3.2	10
C6	208	2.9	10
C7	213	6	10

Fig. 15. Arrangements of three copper flanges to replicate a full lid circumference. The three arms of the ultrasonic reader shown in Fig. 9 are each positioned on one copper flange.

acquired by a probe kept perpendicular to the welding area. In particular, this signal is examined in contrast to the internal gap amplitude echo acquired before chamfers machining using a probe with 0° inclination placed at a height of 15 mm.

Fig. 16. Ultrasonic amplitude responses of chamfers (in yellow) and the internal gap (in blue) on variations of the transducer's angle of displacement.

Fig. 17. Comparison between the amplitude response of the internal gap acquired by a 15° inclined probe (continuous line) and a 0° inclined probe (dashed line).

In this way, it is possible to demonstrate that the authentication fingerprint could be acquired not only by a probe perpendicular to the welding area but also by the inclined probe with the beam splitter. As reported in Fig. 17, the Pearson's correlation index ρ between the two curves is 0.9; the index is calculated according to the following equation where cov is the covariance, σ_X is the standard deviation of curve X , and σ_Y is the standard deviation of curve Y

$$\rho_{X,Y} = cov(X, Y) / \sigma_X \sigma_Y. \quad (2)$$

As a result, the new version of the ultrasonic acquisition device allows not only the detection of a chamfers code but also a complete acquisition of the internal gap echo due to the adoption of a single probe and beam splitter.

Like the internal gap measurements, the amplitude response of chamfers has been compared with the response acquired by the same probe inclined at 15° and with the same height, water path, and temperature, before the machining of chamfers on the flange. As expected, considering the maximum amplitude within the same time window (gate 1), the amplitude response acquired is almost flat due to the absence of chamfers (see Fig. 18). In order to verify the presence or absence of a chamfer, an amplitude threshold can be considered. In particular, if the amplitude of the ultrasonic response in gate 1 is above 100, a chamfer is detected. Observing the amplitude responses of each chamfer, the best compromise is to not affect

Fig. 18. Comparison between the amplitude response within gate 1 acquired by a 15° inclined probe before and after the realization of chamfers on the flange. The dashed line represents the response before chamfer machining, and the continuous line is the response after chamfer machining.

Fig. 19. Angular matching between the identification code (yellow signal) and the authentication fingerprint of the internal gap (blue signal). A third unique fingerprint (green curve) can be realized by simply connecting the intersection points between the two signals.

the copper too much and ensure a robust chamfer detection pattern, even for the smaller chamfer C3, 6-mm wide, and with an angular extension of 3°.

The testing of the ultrasonic acquisition device points out the possibility of acquiring both the identification and the authentication fingerprints simultaneously. Moreover, the angular matching between the two curves can be obtained by simply connecting the intersection points between them. The third fingerprint is obtained by merging the other two and is illustrated in Fig. 19.

Following the test of the new device on a copper flange with chamfers, it is important to analyze the performance of the device for potential implementation in the field. For this purpose, Section IV discusses how the system could be further optimized in relation to the safeguarding requirements imposed by authorities.

IV. DISCUSSION OF A PORTABLE ULTRASONIC ACQUISITION DEVICE FOR FIELD TESTS

The introduction of a beam splitter within the ultrasonic acquisition system for canisters enables the use of only one transducer instead of two for the acquisition of both the identification and authentication fingerprints. However, the applica-

Fig. 20. Drawing of a potential setup for the implementation of the ultrasonic acquisition device at the encapsulation plant. Reference fingerprints could be acquired after the radiographic inspection of the weld (radiographic station in blue) due to the deposition of the ultrasonic acquisition device (in red) above the lid by a crane (in green).

tion of the device in the field (i.e., in the encapsulation plant and the geological repository) requires the improvement of some electronic features to fulfill the safeguards and security requirements. For this purpose, potential on-site implementation of the ultrasonic device has been discussed, and a solution for the improvement of electronic performance has been proposed by the description of the SFAD.

A. On-Site Implementation of the Ultrasonic Acquisition Device

According to the Swedish method, fuel assemblies will be inserted in copper tubes with iron inserts, and the copper lid will then be friction stir-welded onto the tube at the encapsulation plant [16]. After welding, nondestructive testing will be carried out to verify the quality of the weld, and after that, the canisters will be machined (part of the lid will be removed to reach the final geometry). Canisters will undergo an X-ray inspection at the radiographic station, and at that stage, the ultrasonic acquisition device could be placed over the canister by a crane and remotely activated for the recording of reference fingerprints (see Fig. 20).

According to the safeguards requirements, the recording of fingerprints should be performed by an inspector in order to ensure the security of the previously and currently acquired ultrasonic fingerprints. However, since the disposal of the fuel in copper canisters requires the management of a large number of canisters, inspectors should operate/work on-site over a long period of time. In order to avoid the need for inspectors to be present, which is onerous, expensive, and even dangerous with the level of radiation in the measurement room, the ultrasonic acquisition device should be modified to include a remote control for autonomous measurement. In this way, all the data could be recorded and send to a remote control station over a secure wireless connection. Another important need for the implementation of the ultrasonic acquisition device in the field is the necessity of water for immersion testing. To date, the ultrasonic acquisition device is able to complete a round of the canister circumference in about 4 min. This time could be too long within the handling chain of a canister, most of all in the case of verification of fingerprints at the geological repository. In fact, while the ultrasonic inspection

Fig. 21. Photographs of an assembled SFAD with 180 mm of side length (left) and the designed electronic control board (right). IP64 external connectors and touch screens have been used for on-site testing (for example, in a geological repository).

in the encapsulation plant could benefit from the presence of a socket for the power supply or a crane for deposition of the device, in the geological repository, the ultrasonic test should be performed by a portable device able to implement a fast acquisition. Measured data can then be compared with references to verify the correlation between them and any potential signal anomalies. The acquisition time could be improved modifying the control box of the device and replacing the electronic module (US-KEY) for the transmission and reception of signals. According to the above-mentioned requirements, it has been decided to design and realize a new electronic system for the realization of a portable reader, called SFAD.

B. Optimization of the Ultrasonic Acquisition System With the SFAD

The SFAD is an innovative customized system able to quickly perform ultrasonic testing and send acquired fingerprints to a remote control unit. The device, requested by the Joint Research Centre of the European Commission, has been developed by the University of Florence with the aim of upgrading a currently used reading system for the ultrasonic acquisition of seals' fingerprints from stainless steel seals. However, due to the modular device architecture, the new instrument allows a flexible use for different types of acquisition that require different ultrasonic probes, different motors (stepper, synchronous ac), different data storage (wireless transmission and local memory card), and software user interface. This flexibility is obtained by programming the firmware of the two microcontrollers and the touch screen processor. The adaption of the SFAD to copper canister fingerprint acquisitions has been preliminarily presented in [17]. The portability of the device is obtained by arranging the various system components in a custom plastic case realized with a 3-D printer (PLA) with a maximum side dimension of 180 mm and a weight of 2.3 kg, including the rechargeable LiFePO₄ battery (see Fig. 21). Moreover, the device can be wirelessly connected to a PC where it is possible to set the main parameters of the ultrasonic inspection, control the start and stop of the motor, and process received data. On the local display, it is possible to monitor the progression of the ultrasonic test and system failure messages.

Fig. 22. Architecture of the SFAD ultrasonic portable reader.

Fig. 23. Comparison between the acquisition of a seal fingerprint by the current reading system (in red) and the new SFAD (in blue). Each sample is acquired with an angular resolution of 0.015°.

The architecture of the SFAD includes different blocks (see Fig. 22). The core of the device is represented by two ATMEL processors (the ATSAM5D44A for the software and the ATSAM4E16E for the firmware) for the control of an asynchronous or synchronous ac motor, the management of the power consumption, the transmission of signals via wireless connection, and the storage of data in an external SD card. The power source is represented by a LiFePO₄ battery pack (12 V, 3.5 Ah), which guarantees a minimum operating time of 5 h. The ultrasonic testing is regulated by the US-SPI module (Lecoer Electronique), which presents an SPI high-speed connection for the transmission/reception of data. Therefore, in contrast to the US-KEY, the US-SPI allows the acquisition of a larger amount of data in a reduced time.

For the sake of simplicity, some tests have been performed on stainless steel seals to verify the replication of the fingerprints acquired with SFAD. An example of ultrasonic responses acquired by the currently used reading system (in red) and by the new SFAD (in blue) is shown in Fig. 23.

Pearson's correlation index between the two fingerprints is 0.9, and it has been demonstrated that the SFAD can replicate the same performances of the JRC reading system even providing new functionalities [18].

The adoption of the SFAD within the ultrasonic acquisition system for copper canisters will introduce new functionalities that satisfy the needs required for the implementation of the device in the field. In particular, the required presence of inspectors could be avoided, and the ultrasonic acquisition could be completely controlled remotely. Due to the transmission of data through an SPI bus, the acquisition time could also be reduced by up to a factor of four with an execution of a complete round in only 1 min instead of 4.

V. CONCLUSION

The proposed innovative ultrasonic method can be used as containment and surveillance measures to recover the continuity of knowledge of spent nuclear fuel in cases of loss during the handling, transport, and disposal of copper canisters. It provides a solution for the identification and authentication of copper canisters based on amplitude angular response obtained by a 10-MHz US immersion probe and a beam splitter. The identification fingerprint, represented by a configuration of chamfers machined around the copper lid circumference before welding, can be acquired by rotating a 15° inclined probe around the lid circumference at a fixed height. The authentication fingerprint, represented by the amplitude response of the internal gap between lid and tube, can be acquired by a rotating probe kept perpendicular to the welding area (at 0° inclination). The implementation of a mirror to split the signal into two different directions allows optimization of the acquisition time and the one-channel electronics in terms of costs, complexity, and power consumption. The testing of the device has been carried out on a copper flange, i.e., a slice of the copper lid already welded onto the tube, where a code of chamfers has been machined. The geometry of chamfers has been designed to optimize the ultrasonic inspection, and CIVA simulations have been implemented to study the variations of the echo amplitude of chamfers. Moreover, the experimental tests on the copper flange with chamfers support the possibility of acquiring a good ultrasonic amplitude echo (with a peak amplitude above the threshold of 100) from chamfers 6-mm wide, 55° inclined, and 3° angularly extended. The testing of the ultrasonic acquisition device also indicated that the internal gap amplitude response could be acquired by an inclined probe due to the adoption of a beam splitter. Finally, the potential implementation of the device within the handling chain of copper canisters has been discussed. The call for a portable device, fast, and remotely accessible by inspectors motivates the need to improve the electronics performance of the device. The SFAD has been designed and implemented to reduce the acquisition time of the ultrasonic system and to perform an automatic inspection of copper canisters. Safeguards Authorities are now in charge of reviewing the proposal for the development of an identification and authentication system to support the continuity of knowledge requirement.

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